

Students' Assessment on the Admission and Retention Policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration of the University of Cebu-Banilad

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Abstract

The admission policy is crucial in guiding students in enrolling in specific programs at the University. At the same time, retention informs the academic department on how to support students based on their academic performance and behavioral patterns. However, the educational arena is highly dynamic; therefore, there is a need to assess these two aforementioned policies in educational institutions. This investigation aims to assess the admission and retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program, to formulate a framework that will guide the revision of these policies. This study applies the descriptive correlation research design. Using the purposive sampling

technique, there will be seven hundred thirteen (713) BSBA students of the University of Cebu-Banilad who served as respondents in this investigation. This study utilized a researcher-made survey and was pilot-tested. Frequency counts, percentages, the Chi-square test of independence, One-Way ANOVA, and simple linear regression were used for data analysis. The Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, as assessed by the students, exceeded their expectations regarding the admission and retention policies. Hence, it helped maintain the preferred educational quality in said program, leading to the attainment of democratic quality education at an affordable cost.

Keywords: *Educational management, admission, retention policy, business administration, correlation, University of Cebu-Banilad, Cebu City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

University education is the apex level of the education system. It is a crucial level of education because it is a stage that prepares students for highly skilled work in various fields, recognizing the critical role that university education plays in the country's overall development. It is expected that university education should inspire and equip students with the desire for self-improvement and the achievement of excellence, as well as relevant skills that will enable them to make the maximum contribution to all facets of the nation's economy (Agboola et al., 2014).

Wang and Shulruf (2013) opined that equity in higher education is primarily related to enhancing access to higher education for underrepresented groups, such as minorities, low-income groups, or any other type of disadvantaged group. The plethora of research in this area primarily focuses on various types of affirmative action, aiming to increase enrollment of underrepresented groups in higher education. In contrast, in equity research, the interaction between equity and quality in higher education is scarce in the context of educational outcomes and quality.

The Business Administration program employs an integrated approach to examine the interrelationships among various functional areas of business and to investigate how the effective coordination of these components can contribute to organizational success. At the end of the program, students are expected to appreciate the economic, social, technological, and legal environments within which all businesses must operate and possess the essential business knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes necessary to lead an organization and achieve desired results effectively. This interdisciplinary and problem-focused program comprises three integrated elements: core business and management education courses, business administration core, and powerful courses. Each major consists of courses designed to develop critical thinking and analytical skills, as well as information and communication technology, human relations, quantitative, and computer skills that graduates need to serve as successful leaders in business organizations. The program also addresses contemporary organizational issues such as global competition, continuous quality improvement, good governance, and the relationship between organizations and various environmental forces, critical components of a global economy (Commission on Higher Education [CHED], 2017).

Since the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration is an interdisciplinary business discipline, the students are expected to acquire various competencies and skills vital to integrate a myriad of knowledge in actual practice after earning the degree. According to the Graduate Management Admission Council [GMAC] (2021), graduates from business schools are expected to adapt to the diversity of business leaders, which is critical to business success. Diversity and multidisciplinary skills are not acquired overnight and must be developed through years of proper training and education. Students are expected to acquire such training during their bachelor's studies. To acquire such skills, retention programs and policies must be implemented to support and encourage employees.

To provide holistic student development, the University of Cebu has implemented an appropriate admission policy for all students who intend to enroll in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program. This policy ensures that they will gain the competencies and skills necessary for success in the business industry and achieve academic success.

The investigation conducted by Deygers and Malone (2019) shows that the concerns and ideas of language assessment literacy (LAL) scholars and those of university admission policymakers may differ substantially. Real-world policy is often shaped by pragmatism and compromise, and policymakers, including those at universities, may overlook empirical findings. Hence, the view of policymakers can be entirely dissimilar from the traditional approach taken in language assessment literacy (LAL).

The Australian College of Natural Health Sciences [ACNHS] (2021) is committed to ensuring its admissions policies and procedures are fair, transparent, ethical, and timely, making study accessible to a diverse range of prospective students. The college developed a policy framework to equip students with the necessary preparation for study, regardless of their academic background. The policy outlines admissions processes and requirements for undergraduate courses only. It also encourages lifelong learning, including formal, informal, and non-formal learning. It provides applicants for admission to the colleges' courses with the opportunity to have relevant, prior learning considered in their application—the overarching principles of fairness, consistency, transparency, and timeliness govern the admission processes. The college is an open-access institution, and admission is granted through the normal tertiary process of direct entry. Prospective students may be admitted through a direct application, provided they can supply certified copies of their previous qualifications and/or experience, which will serve as the basis for admission.

Moreover, Ackerman and Schibrowsky (2007) discussed how retention programs applied in universities are used to monitor policies and ensure the quality of students before they graduate. It is also a form of relationship marketing. It is a concept that focuses on attracting, maintaining, and building business relationships to enhance a business's profitability. The core of the relationship marketing approach in business is that resources are directed toward strengthening ties to existing customers on the proven premise that maintaining existing customers is less costly than attracting new ones. The relationship marketing model presents a distinct approach to student retention, offering a fresh perspective on retention strategies and providing an economic justification for implementing retention programs.

The University of Cebu-Banilad implements a retention policy to ensure that students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program acquire the necessary skills and learning outcomes, ultimately landing a job that aligns with the program's outcomes.

However, retaining students in post-secondary programs has been a national concern for decades. Not everyone is comfortable applying the concepts of retention programs, and doing so remains a challenge. Improving student retention is a worthwhile goal for various individual, social, and economic reasons (Ackerman & Schobrowski, 2007).

Heiden (1998) noted that a review of the literature and research found mixed evidence regarding the effectiveness of student retention. Since retention is an age-old practice, a historical review of the literature was included to inform the reader of the progression of retention in schools.

Moreover, the study results of Heiden (1998) showed that a limited number of students were retained in the schools. Many boys were retained more than girls, and many schools retained no students. The results also showed that many students receiving free lunch were retained. Less than one-half of the surveyed schools had developed a policy on retention. With a remarkably low number of students retained, most retentions resulted from either philosophical or procedural guidelines. Fewer than 50% of the schools surveyed had a formal policy in place. Schools without a formal policy followed essentially the same procedures as those with a formal policy. Approximately one-third of the principals thought that retention led to later academic success. Only 18% of the principals surveyed believed that the teacher should decide on retention.

Although the goals and objectives set to be achieved through university education were clearly stated, the worry is about the disparity between policy and the realization of the stated objectives. Recent evidence has shown a mismatch between the education received and the quality of students produced, as demonstrated in their performances. Furthermore, the emphasis is on the quantitative expansion of education rather than its qualitative improvement in the country. More concern has been focused on the number of educated and graduating students rather than the quality of the graduates (Agboola et al., 2014).

Agboola et al. (2014) further highlighted another issue regarding inconsistencies in educational policies that contribute to poor service delivery in the school system. Furthermore, policies that do not take into account students' academic abilities and the adequacy and quality of resources available in the institutions can be discouraging and frustrating to administrators.

Admission and retention programs and policies are forms of monitoring strategies that universities can use to ensure the quality of their graduates. With this, research is necessary to assess the timeliness and relevance of the current admission and retention policy for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration at the University of Cebu-Banilad, in order to address the current trends and changes in the competencies and skills required in the labor and entrepreneurial markets. In this way, the University will be able to adapt and update the most effective and efficient admission and retention framework that is responsive to the demands of the business industry, remain true to its vision of democratizing quality education, and be a visionary and industry leader, giving hope and transforming lives.

FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in Tinto's theory of student departure, also known as the institutional departure model. The social aspect of persistence is characterized by the student's ability to interact effectively with the social and academic systems within the institution. Tinto mapped out a process that begins with students' associations and expectations in their first year. Those prior associations and expectations can be weakened or strengthened based on how the students are incorporated into the institutional community. A successful corporation might find that those goals change when students shed their connections to old communities, rather than their new community. If student associations and expectations are less malleable, students may find themselves at a higher risk of dropping out (Kinley, 2021).

The theory also specified that student departure or retention has three primary sources. This involves academic difficulties, for which proper admission is essential for students to overcome. Faculty and staff interactions, extracurricular activities, and peer-group interactions are factors. There are also principles to follow for effective retention. These include institutional commitment to students, educational commitment, and a social and intellectual community. Effective retention programs are committed to the students they serve. They prioritize student welfare over other institutional goals. These are first and foremost committed to the education of all, not just some, of their students. Effective retention programs are committed to developing supportive social and educational communities in which all students are integrated as competent members. The theory also specifies that institutions should provide resources for program development and incentives for program participation that reach out to faculty and staff. It should ensure that faculty and staff possess the necessary skills to assist and educate students (Upload Care Incorporated, 2015).

Astin's theory of involvement posits that student involvement refers to the amount of physical and psychological energy students devote to the academic experience. A student's development is directly related to the quantity and quality of student involvement. Admission teams would need to recruit applicants based on their likelihood of becoming involved on campus. This would lead to looking for specific competencies in students, including motivation, time management, and leadership (Sullivan, 2018). This

theory is constructive for administrators and faculty in designing more effective learning environments (Student Weebly, 2021).

Tinto believes that students drop out of their studies before graduating due to their interactions with the university. These interactions can be categorized into four types: academic, social, intellectual integration, or weak commitment to college or university. He recognizes that all students come to campus with unique characteristics, diverse backgrounds, varied passions, and distinct expectations. He also believes that every institution has unique characteristics, and finding a good "fit" between applicants and institutions is key to student retention. While the admissions team's duties may end at finding good "fit" applicants, he also believes that it is the institution's responsibility to provide opportunities for students to integrate socially, intellectually, and succeed academically (Sullivan, 2018).

It was also explained by Braxton (2000) that Astin's theory defined involvement as the central role played by the individual, which determines the extent and nature of growth according to the quality of effort. The theory is based on the Freudian notion of cathexis, in which individuals invest psychological energy in objects outside themselves, such as families, friends, schooling, and jobs.

Student involvement refers to the amount of physical and psychological energy the student devotes to the academic experience. Involvement theory emphasizes the students' behavior; it is what the student does and how they behave that defines and identifies involvement. It emphasizes the student's active participation in the learning process (Student Weebly, 2021). It can occur in various settings, including academic experiences, residence halls, student organizations, athletics, the work environment, or service-learning opportunities. The size and setting of the institution can also influence the type of experience available to the student (Hamrick et al., 2002).

Students benefit from positive interactions with their peers through involvement in extracurricular activities. For students, involvement comes from student engagement. It has two key components that contribute to students' success: the amount of time and how the institutions allocate resources. Students put effort into their studies, and other activities will lead to the experiences and outcomes that constitute their success. The second component is how the institution allocates resources and organizes learning activities to encourage students to participate in and benefit from these activities (Manning et al., 2006).

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The theory also proposed that students must become actively involved in the college environment for learning to occur. Energy can be invested in the academic experience. Involvement must be quantitative and qualitative in nature. It refers both to the actual amount of time

a student devotes to the activity and the seriousness with which the student takes the experience. It also highlights the importance of educators presenting opportunities for students to engage in both in-class and out-of-classroom experiences, thereby encouraging student learning (Hamrick et al., 2002).

Retention is also defined as a longitudinal process incorporating both the student's academic potential and institutional social systems, thus creating a directional model based on the continual variance in social commitments that influence academic performance. It enhances the predictability of conceptual models for a new paradigm that fully recognizes the relationships among external factors (national and educational climate), internal factors (institutional culture and climate), and adaptive factors (sense of place) that affect voluntary dropout decisions in higher education (Kerby, 2015).

The theory also indicated that essential relationships amongst students' initial and later academic goals and commitments are significant. The most considerable direct effect on retention was attributed to initial goals and institutional commitments, followed by later goals and institutional commitments. Academic and social integration constructs can influence the student retention processes. When all of these relationships operate in the best interests of students, appropriate services or programs, such as student support systems, can achieve their maximum benefits (Chrysikos et al., 2017).

Sanford's theory of challenge and support explained how to keep students engaged during their time in a college or university. If they face too many challenges and not enough support, they may retreat, leading to apprehension and unproductive stress. Similarly, if students have too much support but not enough challenge, they can become stagnant. Admissions teams are seeking students who will engage with their school at this intersection of support and challenge, allowing for maximum growth for all students. When students reach maximum growth, they are less likely to transfer or drop out. This increases the school's completion rates, which recruiters can use to attract applicants to their school (Sullivan, 2018).

According to Sanford, college students undergo significant personal growth and development. The college environment itself influences students, including both what happens in and out of the classroom. He believed that a student needs to have a balance of challenge and support for growth and personal development to occur. The basic idea of this theory is that for growth to occur, a person needs a balanced amount of challenge and support as appropriate for the task. Support comes from many sources, including faculty, the dean's office staff, peers, and parents and family members. A significant component of that support stems from the encouragement given to the student to persevere and ask for help (WordPress, 2011).

The theory suggested that the college environment must balance the challenge and support presented to students for student development to occur. Student development occurs most frequently when the two dominant professional subcultures on campus, the faculty and professionals in student affairs and ministry, integrate support and challenge. This dual role of support and challenge is especially relevant to the holistic development of students, where the goals extend beyond cognitive and skill development into values, civic responsibility, and faith development. Faculty and student affairs professionals play vital roles in creating a culture of challenge and support. This culture represents a shift from a historical model where faculty undertook the challenging tasks and student affairs professionals provided support, to a more holistic approach that requires both groups to support and challenge students (Ward et al., 2005).

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) seldom admit college students automatically. They require students to undergo a series of admission examinations. These are usually standard examinations that can only be administered and interpreted by licensed professionals, such as psychologists. These examinations determine one's aptitude, interest, and preparedness for college. Some HEIs use these entrance examinations not as a basis for admission, but for counseling and guidance purposes while the student studies for the chosen degree program. When an HEI does not use entrance exam results as a basis for admission, some HEIs have an open admission system. An open admission system may be paired with a selective retention system. There is also the so-called selective admission system. This is when a high school graduate does not automatically qualify for admission to the university. The series of entrance tests for admission determines whether a student qualifies for a place in the university. If the university places a quota on the number of entrants admitted for a particular school year, it would likely adjust its cut-off score to match that obtained by entrants at the tail end of the desired quota. The pros and cons of this method may be a topic for future discussion. Besides admission quotas for the total number of entrants, there are also quotas in specific programs (Tanhueco-Tumapon, 2015).

The Royal Roads University (2015) opined that admission policies are essential to ensure the university's growth. The objective of admission is to continually improve the quality and responsiveness of the admission process. It also ensures fairness and equitable access to the different programs offered by the university. It streamlines the admissions process with more responsive and customer-oriented services, empowering student applicants. Admission policies ensure that the university's legal liabilities are managed effectively through consistent and appropriate admission processes. To ensure consistency and fairness, standardized evaluation practices will be used to assess applicants' qualifications. There are also several admission decision categories, including unconditional acceptance, conditional acceptance, and rejection. When applicants meet the admissions requirements to the program of study to which they applied, they may be offered unconditional admission. Those applicants who do not meet all the admissions requirements for the program of study to which they applied may be offered acceptance, subject to meeting specified conditions prior to the program's start. Applicants who do not meet the admissions requirements for the

program to which they have applied, have submitted false statements and/or documents, or failed to disclose relevant information will have their applications for admission rejected.

A good admission policy should be transparent, reliable, and valid, selecting candidates based on merit, potential, and diversity, and should adopt a professional approach. School grades and university exams play a crucial role in university entrance worldwide. Transparency, diversity, and professionalism are also common issues in HEIs regarding admission. These issues must be addressed. The admissions policy should also be available to the student. The issue of diversity, including ensuring an equitable ethnic composition and offering opportunities to older individuals who missed out on higher education the first time around or to those who are socially disadvantaged, is one of the most complex areas of higher education (Adolphus, 2021).

Retention policy is another means by which universities uphold and maintain the quality of their students. Retention is repeating an academic year of school. Retention in school is also referred to as grade retention, being held back, or repeating a grade. Grade retention is the opposite of social promotion, in which children continue with their age peers regardless of academic performance. Grade retention is an excellent predictor of who passes the course. Studies spanning several decades suggest that being retained one grade increases the risk of dropping out by 40 to 50 percent. Being retained twice or more almost guarantees the student will drop out. Students who have been retained, even in earlier years, have the same unhealthful behaviors as retained middle-school students and more incidents of driving while using alcohol, marijuana use, suicidal behaviors, and high-risk sexual behavior. Individuals who have repeated a grade are more likely as adults to be unemployed, live on welfare, or be in prison than adults who did not repeat a grade (Encyclopedia of Children's Health, 2021).

Most retention programs are either institution-specific or system-wide in scope. The fundamental of these retention programs is academic support that focuses on the academic skills not acquired in their senior high school. These programs include tutoring. Tutoring is independent in college programs. These may provide a small study group that is most beneficial to students. College retention programs play a significant role in promoting positive student retention. These programs appear to assist in filling the gaps between the students' need to grasp the standard knowledge required for the enrolled program. HEIs can produce good quality graduates who can play a critical role in resolving societal and global issues (Black, 2018).

The study of Ginsberg and Whaley (2003) found that the legal parameters regarding admission and retention fall under the expectations established for other types of professional training. University officials have great latitude to make professional judgments. Most institutions have formal admission and retention policies, though the admission policies are more fully developed. Many universities reported having formal policies to consider student dispositions for teaching, though no single policy is used by more than one-third of the universities surveyed. Teacher preparation programs have more legal latitude than is being employed for admission and retention decisions, and it is recommended that the field establish professional norms for retention policies and assessing student dispositions for teaching.

Moreover, McNelis et al. (2010) revealed that grade point average (GPA) alone should not be the sole determinant of admission. Proper admission criteria should be developed and implemented. There should be a more comprehensive and varied approach to student admission. Admission programs to schools must be kept up-to-date. A systematic study is also needed to determine how the new criteria affect student diversity, examination and course grades, progression, retention, graduation, admission to graduate school, and the satisfaction of faculty and future employers with graduates.

In addition, Leeds et al. (2013) also noted that the primary concern for institutions and instructors is the high dropout rate among students. Retention strategies may not impact retention rates. This is important as faculty are routinely encouraged to implement similar online course design and delivery strategies.

Further, Getzel (2008) stated that support factors help youth and young adults persist and remain in college. Student support factors include services that develop more vital self-determination skills, teach and support young adults' self-management skills, expose students to assistive technology, and promote career development by providing internships or other career-related experiences. Students benefit when faculty

have increased awareness and knowledge of the characteristics and needs of students and when faculty incorporate concepts of universal design into their instruction and curriculum.

Student admission and retention programs must be given importance. Proper admission supports good retention. Hence, Dalangin (2018) has found that academic integration has a relationship with initial goals and institutional commitment than social integration. It was recommended that the university provide extracurricular activities to students. Only the later goals and institutional commitment are significant; this means that the student's commitment to their initial goals is the same commitment that supports their later goals and institutional commitments. However, even though there is significance in the later goals and institutional commitment, it did not guarantee student retention. The factor that resonates behind this may be due to the availability of options that allow students to continue their studies until they graduate.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This investigation assessed the admission and retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program to develop a framework to guide the review and revision of these policies. It specifically seeks to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, year level, major, and type of senior high school from which they graduated; the respondents' assessment of the admission and retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program; and the challenges they encountered. It also reveals a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles, their evaluations of the Bachelor of Science in Business and Administration's admission and retention policies, and the challenges they faced with both policies.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, research environment, respondents, instruments, procedures, statistical treatment and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlation research design to investigate the relationship between the profile of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) students and their assessments of the admission and retention policies, as well as the issues and problems they encountered.

Correlational research is a type of non-experimental research in which the researcher measures two variables and assesses the statistical relationship (i.e., the correlation) between them with little or no effort to control extraneous variables. There are essentially two reasons that researchers interested in statistical relationships between variables would choose to conduct a correlational study rather than an experiment. The first is that they do not believe that the statistical relationship is causal (Price et al., n.d.). Additionally, Curtis et al. (2016) suggest that findings from correlational research can help determine the prevalence and relationships among variables, as well as forecast events based on current data and knowledge.

Research Environment

The study was conducted via an online platform, specifically Google Forms, with Bachelor of Science in Accountancy students from the College of Business and Accountancy at the University of Cebu-Banilad, Cebu City, Philippines.

Research Respondents

The research respondents were the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) students of the University of Cebu-Banilad. Utilizing the probability-purposive sampling technique, two hundred seventy-eight (278) students were requested to answer the self-made survey questionnaire. Inclusion criteria include only bona fide BSBA students enrolled in the school year, 2021-2022, 18 years old and above, and willing to participate in this investigation.

Research Instrument

This research employed a self-designed instrument to collect data. It consisted of three (3) parts. The first (1st) part contains items about the profile of the respondents as to age, gender, year level, and type of senior high school they graduated from. The second (2nd) part contains questions that assess the admission and retention policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program. The third (3rd) part contains questions about the issues and problems encountered.

The self-made questionnaire underwent pilot testing to assess its reliability before administration. Twenty (20) students from the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) program served as the dry-run respondents. The Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.847974 indicates that the survey questionnaire is reliable and suitable for final administration.

Research Procedures

The researchers asked permission from the Dean of the College of Business and Accountancy of the University of Cebu, Banilad. The protocol was then submitted for review at the University of Cebu Research Ethics Committee. Before conducting the data gathering, the researchers provided a short orientation about the study's objectives to the target respondents. Then, they were given a soft copy of the consent form to read ahead of time before being asked to decide whether or not they would participate in the study. Those BSBA students who expressed their willingness to answer the questionnaire were asked to sign an informed consent form.

Moreover, the data gathered were treated with confidentiality. They were stored on the researchers' personal laptop, protected by a password, and only they would have access to the data. Such data will be deleted after five years.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was subjected to the following statistical tool. Frequency counts and percentages were calculated to analyze the profiles of the respondents. Chi-square test of independence was computed to determine the significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and their assessments of the admission and retention policies of the BSBA program at the University of Cebu-Banilad. Further, simple linear regression was applied to determine the correlation between the paired variables.

Ethical Considerations

The proceedings of this research comply with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and ethical research principles. All data gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. Prior to data gathering, the researcher employed virtual means to orient the target respondents about the study. A consent form consists of two parts: the information sheet, which outlines the scope and methodology of the study, and the data privacy agreement/certificate of consent, which was also discussed with the target respondents before they were asked to sign. The orientation emphasized that participation in the study is entirely voluntary and that participants have the freedom to withdraw at any time without any consequences. In the context of beneficence, the research provided benefits to students, faculty members, university administrators, and other educational stakeholders, as the framework will guide and ensure that the admission and retention policy addresses the issues encountered by university stakeholders promptly, in response to the changing educational sector. In the context of the principle of non-maleficence, de-identification of responses and the anonymity of respondents will be practiced. Lastly, in the principle of justice in ethics, all research participants will be treated equally, with no discrimination, and will be afforded the same degree of respect. Since the gathering will be undertaken online, all the electronic data and results will be used by the university to ensure the security of the data. After the results were analyzed and recorded, they were deleted and destroyed electronically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data. The first section presents the profile of the student respondents. The respondents in the study were students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program for A.Y. 2021-2022.

The data in Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, year level, major, and the type of senior high school graduated.

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic Profile (n = 278)

Profiles	Frequency (f)	Percentage(%)
Age		
36-41 years old	2	0.72
30-35 years old	8	2.88
24-29 years old	18	6.47
18-23 years old	250	89.93
Gender		
Male	30	10.79
Female	248	89.21
Year Level		
First year	119	42.81
Second year	18	6.47

Third year	96	34.53
Fourth year	45	16.19
Major		
Financial Management	94	33.81
Marketing Management	66	23.74
Operational Management	68	24.46
Human Resource Management	50	17.99
Type of Senior High School Graduated		
Public	106	38.13
Private	172	61.87

In terms of age, most respondents, at 89.23%, belonged to the 18-23 year age bracket. This result indicates that most students enrolled in the Bachelor of Business Administration (BSBA) program had undergone senior high school under the K to 12 program.

According to the World Education Services [WES] (2022), most of the students graduated from senior high school at the age of 18 years old. This also demonstrates that students enrolled in first-year college are typically aged 18 to 19 years old, and most of them graduate from college, including four-year programs such as BSBA, at the age of 22 to 23.

On the other hand, the data also shows that only two (2) respondents, or 0.72% were 36-41 years old. The students aged 36-41 years old represent either returnee, shiftee, or second-courser students. That is the reason they were past the average age for college students.

US News (2022) reported that not all students pursue college after graduating from high school. Some of these students take time off to work, travel, or face financial issues. These students choose to go to college later in life.

In gender, there were two hundred forty-eight (248) female respondents, representing 89.21% of the total respondents, while there were only thirty (30) or 10.79% male respondents. The data indicate that most students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration are female, as they have a greater interest in careers related to human resources, entrepreneurship, marketing management, operations management, and financial management.

The ratio of women in business schools has increased from around 32% in 2011 to 39% in 2019. The growing efforts within the business world to open up hiring and promotion options to women are now very apparent in the business arena. Compared to 20 years ago, women today are empowered to become entrepreneurs (Business Program Insights, 2021).

Moreover, one hundred nineteen (119) or 42.81% of the respondents were first-year students. The result shows that first-year students. Based on years of experience in enrolment statistics, more students enrolled in a particular program have been in the first-year level, and they have also shown more enthusiasm to respond and participate in this investigation, given that they have lighter academic loads than those in higher year levels.

Thibodeaux et al. (2016) found that first-year students spent less time on academics than on socializing and fulfilling work obligations during their first semester. Students generally planned to spend more time on academics in the second semester.

On the other hand, only eighteen (18) or 6.47% of the respondents were second-year Bachelor of Science in Business Administration students. This figure indicates that only a few sophomore students were able to allocate time to respond to this study.

The North Carolina State University (2022) disclosed that as the year level increases, the demand for time management also increases. College classes may seem complex and draining, and involve more hours of studying.

The data also showed that ninety-four (94) or 33.81% were majors in Business Administration with a focus on Financial Management. The challenges and the promising careers that await graduates of finance-related courses attract the current generation of business students to specialize in financial management.

The BSBA-Financial Management field of business program provides students with a strong foundation in theories, principles, and concepts that equip them with the relevant technical and analytical skills necessary for financial decision-making, while being cognizant of the dynamic domestic and global business environment, and mindful of their role in nation-building. The students' terminal outputs are research undertakings geared toward both applications of learned concepts and/or theory development (University of Santo Tomas [UST], 2020).

On the other hand, fifty (50) respondents, or equivalent to 17.99% of the total number of respondents, took the BSBA major in Human Resource Management course.

The Human Resource Management major prepares its students to possess the necessary skills and competencies that enable them to thrive in any industry and effectively manage an organization's human capital. Students are expected to perform the role of a strategic business partner and perform different human resource functions (The University of Sto. Tomas [UST], 2020).

However, graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Psychology and other business-related courses can also pursue jobs typically held by BSBA majors in Human Resource Management. This means that stiff competition exists in the job market for this field of discipline. Hence, only a few were attracted to take this course.

Additionally, most students have graduated from private academic institutions, comprising 172 BSBA students (61.87%), while 106 respondents (38.17%) graduated from public high schools. This indicates that most students prefer to enroll in private schools for senior high school, as they offer a variety of tracks and strands that students can choose from, unlike public schools with limited resources and offerings.

Barrington (2021) opined that private schools provide a varied and challenging educational experience for students. Private schools often have a reputation for keeping strict standards for discipline and respect. This, combined with a stronger sense of community and lower staff-to-student ratios, makes for a safer school environment. Since private schools are not limited by public funding, they often have access to better resources.

Table 2 presents the respondents' assessment of the admission policies for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration.

Table 2. Respondents' Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program (n =278)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
The admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...		
1. is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	3.32	Strongly Agree

2. is fast and hassle free.	3.27	Strongly Agree
3. encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	3.24	Relatively Agree
4. ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	3.31	Strongly Agree
5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	3.51	Strongly Agree
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	3.44	Strongly Agree
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	3.24	Relatively Agree
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	3.46	Strongly Agree
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	3.28	Strongly Agree
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	3.42	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26- 4.00 - Strongly Agree; 1.76- 2.50 - Agree; 2.51 – 3.25 – Relatively Agree; 1.00- 1.75 – Disagree

The highest weighted mean of 3.51 indicates that the respondents strongly agreed that the admission policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program at the University of Cebu (UC-Banilad) provides equal opportunities to students regardless of their race, gender, and socio-economic status. This denotes that the admission policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration [BSBA] program practices no discrimination and no biases in treating the students and in giving the same degree of opportunity to each student in joining curricular and extracurricular activities.

Woessmann and Peterson (2007) discussed the fact that, although educational research today focuses on assessing reforms to promote equal opportunities among students, many current policies concentrate on allocating additional resources. It was suggested that the tools of economics be used to assess the outcome of efforts to address the problem of equal opportunity in education across a range of countries. Some evidence suggests potential routes for advancement and raises considerable doubts about whether many current school policies are effective in significantly altering the opportunity structure. The evidence also presents questions about the idea that causal peer effects are powerful.

Equality and diversity are about promoting and accepting the differences between people. Equality is about ensuring individuals are treated fairly regardless of their race, gender, age, disability, religion, or sexual orientation. Diversity is about recognizing and respecting these differences. Promoting equality and diversity in education is essential for both teachers and students. This will create a classroom environment where all students can thrive together and understand that individual characteristics make people unique and not 'different' in a negative way (Petty, 2014).

The lowest weighted mean of 3.24 indicates that respondents generally agreed that the admission policies of the BSBA program encourage students to enroll in the program. These results suggest that the promotional activities of the College of Business and Accountancy, which offers the BSBA program, are not particularly effective in enticing incoming first-year students to take this course at the university.

Additionally, a weighted mean of 3.24 indicates that the respondents generally agreed that the admission of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program at UC-Banilad provides flexibility to students by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning processes. The BSBA admission policies employ a spiral progression in learning among students, as they assess past knowledge of the courses to connect with the lessons in the curriculum.

Providing flexible admission is an action taken by higher educational institutions, most especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. The uncertainty brought about by the pandemic forced several governments and higher education institutions to cancel national school-leaving examinations, postpone final university examinations to a later date, and consider alternative and flexible approaches to higher education admissions. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization's [UNESCO] International Institute for Educational Planning has been researching policies and instruments that support flexible learning pathways in higher education, with alternative admissions pathways to higher education being one of the focus areas. Based on extensive stock-taking, international survey data, and eight country case studies, it identifies both recognition of prior learning (RPL) policies and national qualification frameworks (NQFs) as critical enablers of alternative admission routes. Through RPL, learners can have their competencies acknowledged more efficiently, regardless of whether their skills were acquired in formal, informal, or non-formal contexts (Martin & Furiv, 2020).

Furthermore, the overall mean of 3.35 indicates that the respondents strongly agreed that the admission policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program consistently exceeded their expectations. This result suggests that Bachelor of Science in Business Administration students were content and satisfied with the program's admission policies as offered and implemented in the College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) of the University of Cebu.

Equity is sought to enhance access to higher education, as it is scarce. Issues of equity and quality in higher education explore the possible solutions to promoting both. It concludes that admission models aiming to achieve equity in higher education should be more outcomes- rather than process-based (Wang & Shulruf, 2012).

Table 3 reflects the respondents' evaluations of the retention policies implemented by the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program.

Table 3. Respondents' Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program (n =278)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
The retention policy of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...		
1. serves as my motivation to study harder.	3.28	Strongly Agree
2. serves as my guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum.	3.33	Strongly Agree
3. encouraged me in developing a good study habit.	3.24	Relatively Agree
4. enabled me to become a more responsible student.	3.38	Strongly Agree
5. increases my consciousness in maintaining higher grades.	3.19	Relatively Agree

6. enabled me to practice appropriate time management between doing academic and non-academic activities.	3.29	Strongly Agree
7. assures me that the University of Cebu provides quality education at lesser cost.	3.18	Relatively Agree
8. enabled me to feel that ideally deserve my grades as an indicator of academic performance.	3.27	Strongly Agree
9. encourage me to be participative during class discussions and other class activities.	3.25	Relatively Agree
10.enabled me to feel proud of my academic contributions and non-academic accomplishments as part of holistic development	3.26	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.27	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.26- 4.00 - Strongly Agree; 1.76- 2.50 - Agree; 2.51 – 3.25 – Relatively Agree; 1.00- 1.75 – Disagree

The highest weighted mean of 3.38 indicates that respondents strongly agreed that the retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program of the University of Cebu-Banilad enabled them to become more responsible students. These data indicate that such retention policies prompted students to take their academic and non-academic subjects seriously, ensuring they could comply with the various course requirements to achieve success and complete the degree on time.

Friedman and Mandel (2018) noted that student retention and performance in higher education are crucial issues for educational institutions, educators, and students. Students' high school grade point average, SAT scores, or motivation did not predict retention after one year. A good retention program can increase a student's motivation to study more effectively and stay in school.

On the other hand, the respondents relatively agreed that the BSBA retention policies ensured that the university provides quality education at a lesser cost, based on the lowest weighted mean of 3.18. The mission of the University of Cebu is to provide affordable, high-quality education that responds to the demands of local and international communities.

Student retention is one of seven institutional indicators of quality teaching and learning utilized by the

government for the allocation of teaching and learning performance. It is also one of four indicators used to assess institutions' equity performance. A significant impact is the dramatic transformation of the student body due to economic imperatives for a more skilled workforce in the competitive global world. At the same time, governments are now concerned with the quality of education provided in higher education and have implemented quality assurance measures. The increasingly competitive global higher education market also means that an institution's reputation is reflected in the quality of its graduates. In this setting, student dropout has become a concern due to its implications for the program's quality and the graduates, including the degree to which programs can cater to students from diverse groups (Crosling et al., 2008).

Moreover, the respondents assessed the retention policies implemented by the BSBA program as excellent, based on an overall weighted mean of 3.27. The respondents strongly agreed that the implementation of the BSBA retention policies had exceeded their expectations and believed that it contributes to molding students into becoming competitive and skilled in the labor and entrepreneurial arenas.

Thomas (2021) stated that students from diverse backgrounds today have higher expectations of higher education, which is a result of increased student diversity. Consequently, many students require greater flexibility within their higher education experience and a more relevant curriculum that relates to their own experiences and future aspirations, providing clarity about how to succeed in higher education. Curricular, pedagogical, and assessment strategies need to be overhauled to engage and enable a more diverse student population, juggling complex lives, to maximize the value of contact time and succeed in their higher education and beyond. Student retention today means seeking to assure equity of opportunity for all twenty-first-century students through institutional transformation, rather than the notion that students need to change to fit into and benefit from an outmoded higher education system. It also discusses the need to improve student engagement and sense of belonging by transforming the higher education experience. It advocates for a whole-institution approach to change, involving partnerships within and across institutions and sectors to effect and sustain this transformation.

This section presents the challenges encountered by the respondents in the admission process for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program. Table 4 shows the data.

The highest weighted mean of 2.46 indicates that respondents agreed that one of the challenges they commonly encountered in the admission procedure for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program was the slow response of admission personnel in responding to their questions and queries in selected instances.

When school personnel respond too slowly to students' inquiries, they become frustrated, especially if the issue requires urgent action. Additionally, problems with faulty student personnel services result in a bottleneck in the enrollment process. A slow response to queries is a challenge, especially since the University of Cebu's enrollment process is currently bi-modal, combining both online and face-to-face modes, due to the prohibition on face-to-face classes to curb the rapid transmission of the COVID-19 virus.

Newberry (2022) identified several issues contributing to enrollment declines, including ineffective leadership, staffing issues, quality and satisfaction concerns, environmental concerns, and inadequate enrollment marketing plans. Additionally, situations where the head of the school cannot provide visionary and inspirational leadership are another problem that contributes to enrollment decline. Staffing issues and the slow response of enrollment and admission staff are probably the common reasons why students experience a decrease in motivation to enroll. This requires intentional and proactive work, and it must involve the right staff. Believe it or not, there are still schools that have not appointed a full-time enrollment or marketing director. The right staff must do the right things at the right time in order to move enrollment in the right direction.

Table 4. Challenges Encountered in the Admission of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program (n=278)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Insufficiency of well-defined departmental procedure in enrolling students.	2.28	Agree

2. The lengthy admission process upsets the enrollees applicant's opportunity to be admitted in the BSBA program.	1.91	Agree
3. Lack of entrance examination to the enrollees leads to the influx of academically unprepared students who experienced problems in passing the subjects/course in the BSBA curriculum.	2.45	Agree
4. There is preferential treatment of enrollees.	1.89	Agree
5. Students who are admitted in the BSBA program failed to meet industry requirements.	1.95	Agree
6. Paper-based enrollment system discouraged students to enroll especially in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic.	2.18	Agree
7. Online enrollment system is too slow.	2.23	Agree
8. The admission personnel are too slow in responding to questions and queries of the student.	2.46	Agree
9. The university's official website and the department's Facebook page do not update regularly the announcements for the admission policies and procedures.	2.11	Agree
10. It is too difficult to access the enrolment student's portal.	2.44	Agree
Overall Mean	2.19	Agree

The respondents agreed that, in a few instances, they experienced preferential treatment of enrollees, as indicated in the lowest weighted mean of 1.89. Having preferential treatment in the admission process could discourage students from enrolling, as they may feel that school personnel are not treated equally. It can also tarnish the university's reputation due to its admission policies, as students may not adhere to them because of concerns about discrimination. It is best to follow the admission policies of the BSBA program objectively.

The political treatment admissions policy matters for student incentives and student-body diversity in equilibrium. Preferential treatment policies in college admissions often take or are perceived to take an additive form, where a fixed number of points augments the applicant's score from a disadvantaged background. Such a preferential treatment policy fails to incentivize students from deprived backgrounds. Despite affirmative action, the level of preferential treatment that achieves academic excellence leaves student-body diversity unchanged compared with a background-blind admissions policy and leads to a higher intergroup score gap (Pastine & Pastine, 2012).

Furthermore, the overall mean of 2.19 indicates that respondents agreed that, in a few instances, they experienced various challenges in the admission policies and procedures implemented by the University of Cebu for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program. This data indicates that numerous, albeit minor, loopholes and shortcomings emerged in the enrollment process for the BSBA program. Although not all BSBA students faced such issues, they were not negligible; yet, they call for immediate review and response to mitigate the adverse impact on enrollment.

Oanda (2020) revealed an increasing demand for access to higher education and a crisis of graduate unemployment. These issues have resulted in a complex mix of policies that regulate admission and standards.

Burke and McManus (2011) found that the admissions policy problematically conflates notions of fairness and transparency, failing to address complex socio-cultural inequalities in recognizing the potential student-subject. The study also focused on individual practices rather than on policy discourses and processes of subjective construction, which helps to hide the ways that potential is constructed in ways that privilege and recognize particular student subjectivities.

Table 5 presents data on the challenges encountered by Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) students regarding retention policies.

Table 5. Challenges Encountered in the Retention of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program (n =278)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I find it hard to finish the degree on time based on the curriculum.	1.78	Agree
2. I have high tendency to dropout from the BSBA program.	2.45	Agree
3. My academic and personal expectations in taking the BSBA program was unclear.	2.33	Agree
4. I feel discouraged because I cannot meet the standards set by the teachers in the class.	2.41	Agree
5. I experienced challenges in connecting with the other students or the students' social group.	2.36	Agree
6. The personnel at the Registrar's Office does not assist the student's needed assistance and help.	2.11	Agree
7. The personnel at the Clinic did not provide appropriate medical and dental services.	1.78	Agree
8. The personnel at the Guidance Center did not provide activities/support to help students who experienced difficulty in their enrolled subjects.	1.80	Agree
9. The personnel at the Student Affairs Office did not provide appropriate assistance to the students' and request for assistance.	1.89	Agree
10. I encountered difficulty in adjusting to university's online teaching and learning climate.	2.44	Agree
Overall Mean	2.14	Agree

The highest weighted mean of 2.45 indicates that respondents disclosed a high tendency to drop out of the BSBA program in a few instances. Given the academic requirements and standards in the BSBA

program, students often experience difficulties in passing the courses in the curriculum, and some may feel discouraged from continuing to pursue the degree. However, the complexities in the course requirements are designed to prepare the students for the business world.

Lee and Choi (2010) identified three main categories of factors that influenced the decision of sixty-nine students to drop out: student, course, program, and environmental factors. There are strategies to address these issues, such as understanding each student's challenges and potential, providing quality course activities, a well-structured support system, addressing environmental issues, and managing emotional challenges.

The lowest weighted mean of 1.78 indicates that respondents also agreed that, in some instances, they had difficulty completing the degree on time according to the curriculum. The antecedent to the lateness in completing the degree requirements is financial in nature, or failing accounting subjects, which they find difficult.

Another weighted mean of 1.78 indicates that respondents reported experiencing difficulties in accessing appropriate medical and dental services from the university clinic personnel. The BSBA curriculum is designed in accordance with the Commission on Higher Education standards, suggesting that students be full-time to complete it within four years. This is the reason why most students who work simultaneously struggle to complete the program within a four-year term. On the other hand, the university dentist is not serving full-time in the clinic, and the absence of face-to-face classes hindered the students from availing of dental services amid the COVID-19 pandemic.

Beard (2018) disclosed that almost half of the college students tend not to finish it. One reason is immaturity or fear. A great deal of immaturity is often driven by fear. When students are more interested in learning than staying in their comfort zone, these common problems will not affect them. Another reason is the lack of guidance and support, which often results in students switching majors frequently. Lastly, the most significant reason is academic unpreparedness. There is considerable variation in academic demands in higher education. Being unprepared would result in not completing the degree as stipulated in the curriculum.

Moreover, to motivate students, accessibility to the appropriate medical and dental services that the university offers is also a factor. Bezem et al. (2017) also noted that the organization of health assessments by preventive health services, focusing on children's health and educational performance needs, needs to be improved due to evolving health priorities, including mental health problems, reduced budgets, and shortages of physicians and nurses. The triage approach is a more appropriate method to use in a highly populated university to serve students adequately. Schools using the triage approach had more contact with students and were more satisfied with the appropriateness of support from students than respondents in the approach-as-usual group.

The overall mean of 2.14 indicates that the respondents agreed they had experienced challenges with the retention policies implemented by the BSBA program. It means that they have encountered these challenges in a few instances. Retention in the BSBA program is one of the challenges that the department usually experiences. As the year level of the students increases, the population somewhat decreases. This can be reflected in the degree of difficulty of the courses, which also increases as the year level increases.

Mooring (2016) noted that poor retention is related to students' abilities and a lack of necessary interventions by faculty, beginning with the admission process and continuing throughout the curriculum. Alterations should be made in the recruitment and student selection process. Aggressive academic advising strategies should be implemented, and retention programs should be interwoven into the nursing curriculum. Therefore, student retention is a multifaceted issue that requires a multi-modal approach. Changes in recruitment, implementation of academic advising, and curriculum integration can help correct the problem.

This section presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles in terms of age, gender, year level, primary school, and type of senior high school they graduated from, and their assessment of the admission policies implemented by the BSBA program.

Table 6. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Age and their Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age & admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...					
1. is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	18.114	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	17.234	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
3. encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	19.901	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
4. ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	17.349	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	18.519	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	18.118	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	19.917	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	18.834	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	19.002	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	21.452	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	18.844	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

Table 6 shows a significant relationship between respondents' age and their assessment of the admission policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Program, as indicated by the average computed value of the Chi-square statistic of 18.844, which is greater than the critical value of 16.919. These results indicate that the age of the respondents was associated with their assessment of the admission policies in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, at a 5% level of significance. Hence, the students' age and life cycle influenced their expectations and satisfaction with their admission procedures and process.

Matta et al. (2016) opined that students who delayed their first-grade enrollment tend to have higher aptitude test scores and a higher probability of admission. The advantaged student-applicants also earn more early in their careers. The perception that maturity plays a vital role in school learning has encouraged parents and teachers to delay children's enrollment in first grade. Consequently, there has been a significant increase in the age at which children enter school. College applicants older than their classmates in the first grade are more likely to be admitted to a flagship university right after high school.

Table 7 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' gender and their assessment of the admission policies for the BSBA program.

Table 7. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Gender and their Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Gender & admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad					
1. is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	4.119	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	6.934	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
3. encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	5.678	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
4. ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	6.923	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	5.234	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	6.781	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	5.234	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship

8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	6.113	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	7.913	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	6.345	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
Factor Average	6.127	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' gender and their assessment of the admission policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, as revealed by the average computed value of the Chi-square statistic of 6.127, which is less than the critical value of 7.815. This data indicates that the difference in the sexual preference of gender BSBA students had no connection to their expectations of the procedures imposed during enrollment for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program at a 5% level of significance.

Higher education opportunities have been equalized between genders. The expansion of college admissions has contributed to gender equality in higher education opportunities. Two significant changes occurred: first, women whose parents have a middle education level received more opportunities to pursue higher education; and second, women from rural areas are less disadvantaged in obtaining higher educational opportunities. Compared to the trend before the expansion of higher education admissions, gender equality has shifted from groups with higher parental educational levels to those with lower parental educational levels, and from urban to rural areas (Zhang & Chen, 2014).

Table 8 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' year levels and their assessment of the admission policies of the BSBA program.

Table 8. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Year Levels and their Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Year Level &					
The admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...					
1. is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	17.451	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	18.115	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
3. encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	14.978	9	16.919	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
4. ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	18.119	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	19.004	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	19.564	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	14.892	9	16.919	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	17.923	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	18.115	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	20.345	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	17.851	9	16.919	Reject	Significant Relationship

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' year level and the assessment on the admission policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program in terms of ease and convenience in enrolment, fast and hassle free, ensuring consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants, providing equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status, contributing to raising the standard and quality of the students, giving hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree, making student comfortable of the BSBA course, and making student proud of taking the course as shown in the average computed value of Chi-square of 17.851, which is greater than the critical value of 16.919. These results suggest that the year level of the respondents can influence their perspectives on enrollment in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program.

These results denote that the variation in the year level of the students at the time of the survey connects to their anticipation and satisfaction towards the admission policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Program at the University of Cebu-Banilad, since their ability to evaluate the program relates to their age, exposure to the program, and maturity level.

Epple et al. (2006) disclosed an equilibrium model of the market for higher education. It predicts student selection into institutions of higher education, financial aid, educational expenditures, and educational outcomes. The model gives rise to a strict hierarchy of colleges that differ in the educational quality provided to students, along with a new estimation procedure that exploits the observed variation in prices within colleges. Identification is based on variation in endowments and technology. It does not rely on observed variation in potentially endogenous characteristics of colleges, such as peer quality measures and expenditures. Therefore, the level of difficulty varies based on the year level.

Table 9 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' course major and their assessments of the admission policies of the BSBA program.

Table 9. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Course Major and their Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Course major & admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...					
1. is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	20.365	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	12.308	9	16.919	Accept Ho	Not Significant Relationship
3. encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	14.789	9	16.919	Accept Ho	Not Significant Relationship
4. ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	18.312	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	17.115	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	19.341	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	14.115	9	16.919	Accept Ho	Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	12.545	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Not Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	12.453	9	16.919	Accept Ho	Not Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	13.781	9	16.919	Accept Ho	Not Significant Relationship
Factor Average	15.512	9	16.919	Accept	Not Significant Relationship

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' course major and their assessment on the admission policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration program in terms ease of enrolment, ensuring consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants, providing equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status, contributing to raising the standard and quality of the students and providing flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process, based on the computed values of Chi-square, which were higher than the critical values. This means that the difference in the students' field of academic concentration had a close connection to their opinion on how well the enrollment procedures were undertaken.

Milsom and Coughlin (2015) also found that college students' feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their college major and admission policies resulted from reflection on the information they had learned about themselves and their careers. Some of these referred to extensive self-reflection following increased career awareness and exposure to various occupations. Regardless of how they initially chose their college major, they described a similar pattern of growing satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their major. Opportunities to interact with others and engage in their majors in various ways served as critical catalysts for increasing self and career awareness, and either satisfaction or dissatisfaction emerged as the participants developed a clearer sense of themselves and their goals.

Table 10 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the types of senior high school graduates and their assessment of the admission policies for the BSBA program.

Table 10. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Types of Senior High School Graduated of the Respondents and the Assessment on the Admission Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Types of Senior High School Graduated &					
The admission of BSBA program in UC-Banilad...	9.564	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
1.is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	8.451	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	9.112	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
3.encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	8.072	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
4.ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	9.345	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
5.provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	8.112	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	9.234	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	8.119	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	10.567	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	11.543	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	8.112	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	9.112	3	7.815	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

There is a significant relationship between the types of senior high school from which respondents graduated and their assessment of the admission policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Program, as indicated by the average computed values of the Chi-square value of 9.112, which is greater than the critical value. This means that the difference in the senior high school administration where the BSBA students graduated was associated with their opinions on the procedures for admitting students to the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program.

The type of senior high school is significant, for it serves as a foundation for college years. It is a great time to learn, explore, and develop. Senior high school students need to prepare for the challenges they will face when they start their college education journey. Choosing a senior high school strand is an excellent way to prepare for college, as it benefits the student in multiple ways if they take the most challenging classes available. Many schools offer advanced classes to prepare students academically for college. Getting involved in extracurricular activities is also another tip. Involvement in activities outside of schoolwork makes senior high school a lot more exciting and fun. These extracurricular activities also provide opportunities to acquire proficiencies that cannot be learned through textbooks and tests alone. They can develop essential skills through extracurricular activities, such as teamwork, public speaking, creativity, leadership, and self-awareness. All in all, the type of senior high school is an essential factor in preparing for college (University of Portland [UP], 2022).

Table 11 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' age and their assessment of the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 11. Results on Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Age and their Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age & retention policy of BSBA program in UC-Banilad					

1. serves as my motivation to study harder.	8.456	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
2. serves as my guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum.	9.114	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
3. encouraged me in developing a good study habit.	10.562	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
4. enabled me to become a more responsible student.	12.11	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
5. increases my consciousness in maintaining higher grades.	4.308	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
6. enabled me to practice appropriate time management between doing academic and non-academic activities.	5.423	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
7. assures me that the University of Cebu provides quality education at lesser cost.	6.012	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
8. enabled me to feel that ideally deserve my grades as an indicator of academic performance.	8.456	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
9. encourage me to be participative during class discussions and other class activities.	9.112	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
10.enabled me to feel proud of my academic contributions and non-academic accomplishments as part of holistic development	8.118	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	8.167	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship

There are significant relationships between the respondent's age and their assessment on the retention policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration program in terms serves as their motivation to study harder, serves as their guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum, encouraged them in developing a good study habit, enabled them to feel that ideally deserve their grades as an indicator of academic performance, enabled them to become a more responsible student, enabled them to feel that ideally deserve their grades as an indicator of academic performance, encouraged them to be participative during class discussions and other class activities, based on the computed values of Chi-square of 8.167 which are higher than the critical value of 7.8815. These results suggest that the differences in respondents' age levels and maturity are related to their evaluations of the policies regarding the retention of students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program at the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Bennett (2003) explained the students' decisions to withdraw from their business studies degree courses. It emerged that financial hardship exerted a significant influence on the stay-or-quit decision, moderating the impact of academic performance and the student's level of commitment to their enrolled program on the decision to leave. Individual self-esteem played a crucial role in encouraging or discouraging withdrawal when a person experienced low grades or substantial financial problems. Maturity and students' age are critical factor that contributes to self-esteem. Students' age was more closely connected to satisfaction than to commitment.

Table 12 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' gender and their assessment of the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 12. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Gender and their Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Gender &					
The retention policy of BSB program in UC-Banilad...					
1. serves as my motivation to study harder.	4.679	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
2. serves as my guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum.	5.117	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
3. encouraged me in developing a good study habit.	4.876	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
4. enabled me to become a more responsible student.	5.112	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
5. increases my consciousness in maintaining higher grades.	6.901	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
6. enabled me to practice appropriate time management between doing academic and non-academic activities.	3.11	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
7. assures me that the University of Cebu provides quality education at lesser cost.	7.112	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
8. enabled me to feel that ideally deserve my grades as an indicator of academic performance.	5.234	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
9. encourage me to be participative during class discussions and other class activities.	5.901	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship

10.enabled me to feel proud of my academic contributions and non-academic accomplishments as part of holistic development	6.789	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship
Factor Average	5.483	3	7.815	Accept Ho	No Significant Relationship

There is no significant relationship between respondents' gender and their assessment of the retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, as indicated by the average computed values of the Chi-square statistic, which are less than the average critical value of 5.483 and also less than the average critical value of 7.815. These results indicate that the dissimilarities in the BSBS students' gender did not influence their evaluation of the rules and procedures for retaining students in the specified academic business-related program.

David (2015) stated that the history of gender equality and feminism entering academia marked a change and educational expansion linked to other major social transformations, including the feminist movement. Its effects have been widely felt, such that women now participate in education and employment on unprecedented levels. Indeed, it has opened up opportunities for women in education and employment, including individual and social mobility. It showed how it opened up opportunities for women from middle-class and working-class backgrounds to be the first in their families to attend university.

Table 13 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' year levels and their assessment of the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 13. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between Respondents' Year Levels and their Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Year Level & The admission of BSBA program in UC- Banilad...					
1.is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	18.112	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	17.345	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
3.encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	18.954	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
4.ensures consistency and fairness in	17.114	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

assessing enrollees/applicants.					
5. provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	20.562	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	17.893	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	18.452	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	17.113	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	18.345	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
10. makes student proud of taking the course.	17.116	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	18.101	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

There is a significant relationship between respondents' year level and their assessment of the retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, as reflected in the average computed Chi-square value of 18.101, which is greater than the average critical value of 16.919. These data indicate that the year level of BSBA students was associated with their mindset in evaluating the retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program.

Student retention is a critical component of strategic success in widening participation in the higher education sector. The most significant driver for higher educational institutions in their engagement with retention work is a concern with the student experience, progression, and success. The standard definition of retention, in terms of progression from the first year to the second year, has limited applicability for part-time study or flexible programs. It is challenging to find better and more widely recognized metrics to account for student progression and success in these contexts. There are significant variations in retention rates by protected characteristic, between institutions, and within disciplines across institutions. Systematic collection and monitoring of retention data occur across the higher education sector. Interoperability between different databases is a challenge for many institutions. Retention is a complex, multi-factorial

challenge. Describing and monitoring what happens at all year levels of the system is relatively straightforward (Gilmour & Cannel, 2019).

Table 14 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' primary interests and their assessment of the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 14. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Major and their Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Course Major & assessment on the admission policies of BSBA of UC-Banilad &					
1.is easy and convenient for the enrollees.	18.567	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
2. is fast and hassle free.	17.456	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
3.encourages students to enroll in the BSBA program.	18.119	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
4.ensures consistency and fairness in assessing enrollees/applicants.	17.803	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
5.provides equal opportunities to students irrespective of race, gender, and socio-economic status.	19.456	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
6. contributes to raising the standard and quality of the students.	17.432	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
7. provides flexible admission by acknowledging prior learning attained through informal learning process.	19.045	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
8. gives hope to the students to study and earn the BSBA degree.	18.349	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
9. makes student comfortable of the BSBA course.	20.563	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

10. makes student proud of taking the course.	21.892	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	18.868	9	16.919	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' course major and their assessment of the retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program at the University of Cebu-Banilad, as reflected in the average computed Chi-square value of 18.868, which is greater than the average critical value of 16.919. These results suggest that students' major academic concentrations are linked to their expectations and satisfaction with the program retention policies.

Improving college student retention and graduation rates is a primary focus of higher education nationwide. Scholars have found that students who enter college undecided and are still exploring majors need much support to be retained. Between 20% and 50% of entering freshmen have not selected a major course of study, and colleges and universities are concerned that these students are at a higher risk of dropping out of the institution. Students who remained undecided after the first year were more likely to leave college. This highlights the importance of providing undecided students with a wealth of information in their first year to help them understand themselves and their major academic subjects. Academic advising is a vital campus resource that helps students build connections and develop relationships on campus. Relationships with academic advisors help alleviate some of the initial fears and frustration associated with being undecided, and encourage students to take risks in selecting a major. Effective academic advising services help students make both educational and personal decisions. Choosing a major, deciding on a career, meeting the educational requirements for that career, and overcoming obstacles are the most significant issues for new first-year college students, and these can be addressed through academic advising (Dennis, 2007).

Table 15 displays the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' type of senior high school where they graduated and their assessment of the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 15. Results on the Test of Significant Relationship between the Respondents' Types of Senior High School Graduated and their Assessment on the Retention Policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Chi-Square	df	Critical Value	Decision	Interpretation
Types of SHS Graduated & The retention policy of BSB program in UC-Banilad...					
1. serves as my motivation to study harder.	10.234	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
2. serves as my guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum.	9.119	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship

3. encouraged me in developing a good study habit.	5.671	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
4. enabled me to become a more responsible student.	4.873	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
5. increases my consciousness in maintaining higher grades.	3.678	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
6. enabled me to practice appropriate time management between doing academic and non-academic activities.	10.456	3	7.815	Accept	Significant Relationship
7. assures me that the University of Cebu provides quality education at lesser cost.	7.451	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship
8. enabled me to feel that ideally deserve my grades as an indicator of academic performance.	8.934	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
9. encourage me to be participative during class discussions and other class activities.	8.113	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
10.enabled me to feel proud of my academic contributions and non-academic accomplishments as part of holistic development	9.567	3	7.815	Reject	Significant Relationship
Factor Average	7.81	3	7.815	Accept	No Significant Relationship

There are significant relationships between the respondents' types of senior high school where they graduated and their assessment on retention policies of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration program at the University of Cebu-Banilad regarding serves as my motivation to study harder, serves as my guide to perform better in the various courses in the curriculum, enabled me to feel that ideally deserve my grades as an indicator of academic performance, encourage me to be participative during class discussions and other class activities and enabled me to feel proud of my academic contributions and non-academic accomplishments as part of holistic development as shown in the computed Chi-square values which are lesser than the critical values. Academic preparation that the students obtained in the senio high school level prepared them to attained the requirements of the business administration

progra, especially if their stand that they took is Accounting, business and Management [ABM], which enabled them to take course related to accounting, finance, management and business-related course.

Choosing where to graduate in senior high school is among the most critical decisions. For many families, the choice between attending a private school and a public school arises as part of this conversation. Both types of schools have advantages and disadvantages. The truth is that attending a private versus a public school depends more on the individual student and family than any other factor. Therefore, the most crucial thing in making this decision is the child's goals and needs. Student retention and success in higher education do not matter what type of senior high school the student graduated. The essential thing in college success is deciding what program to take (Sparks Admissions, 2021).

Table 16 displays the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and challenges they faced in the admission policies of the BSBA program of th University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 16. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between Respondents' Profile and Challenges Encountered in the Admission of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Paired Variables	Computed Value of X^2	Critical Value of X^2	df	P-Value	Cramer's V	Decision	Interpretation
Admission Policy Assessment & Age	22.05	16.92	9	0.0087	0.8626	Reject	Significant
Gender	1.74	7.82	3	0.6281	0.0791	Accept	Not Significant
Year Level	5.4	16.92	9	0.7981	0.0805	Accept	Not Significant
Major	4.22	16.92	9	0.8963	0.0711	Accept	Not Significant
Types of Senior High School Graduated	4.85	7.82	3	0.1831	0.1321	Accept	Not Significant

There is a significant relationship between respondents' age and the challenges they encountered in the admission policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program at the University of Cebu-Banilad, as indicated by the computed Chi-square value of 22.05, which exceeds the critical value of 16.92. At the same time, the P-value 0.0087 is less than the significance level of 0.05. This result suggests a strong correlation between respondents' maturity level and the significant issues they encountered when enrolling in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program at the university. The maturity of the students has been influential in dealing with complexities in the school. Hence, it also relates to how they hurdle hardships in their studies to attain academic success.

Sansor et al. (2021) reported that age affects admission and, consequently, the relative challenges experienced during the admission process. The admission system creates a waiting game, as gaining

admission in the second quota is nearly impossible without accumulating a substantial amount of age points. If age predicts completion in higher education, this waiting game might be justified. It was also suggested that age should carry less weight in admission decisions and that countries and/or higher education institutions should carefully consider how their admission system affects student incentives and how applicants are selected.

Table 17 presents the results of the test for a significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and the challenges encountered in the retention policies of the BSBA program.

Table 17. Results of the Test of Hypothesis on the Significant Relationship between Respondents' Profile and Challenges Encountered in the Retention of the Bachelor of the Science in Business Administration Program

Variables	Computed Value of X^2	Critical Value of X^2	df	P-Value	Cramer's V	Decision	Interpretation
Age	5.66	16.92	9	0.7734	0.0824	Accept	Not Significant
Gender	4.47	7.82	3	0.215	0.1268	Accept	Not Significant
Year Level	4.94	16.92	9	0.8395	0.077	Accept	Not Significant
Major	10.97	16.92	9	0.2778	0.1147	Accept	Not Significant
Types of Senior High School Graduated	5.18	7.82	3	0.1591	0.1365	Accept	Not Significant

There is no significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the challenges they encountered in the retention policy of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program, as indicated in the computed values of Chi-square, which is less than the critical values. At the same time, the P-value is greater than the 0.05 alpha value. These results indicate a lack of correlation between BSBA students' demographic characteristics and the hitches and problems they experienced in passing the requirements to complete the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration degree.

Seven constructs can influence student retention. Academic advising, social connectedness, student involvement, faculty and staff approachability, business procedures, learning experiences, and student support services. It was suggested that institution-wide improvement of classroom practices is essential for driving up retention among all students. Academic support, student engagement, and faculty interaction in the classroom can help keep students on track to graduate (Hanover Research, 2014).

CONCLUSIONS

The students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program found that the existing admission and retention policies exceeded their expectations and played a vital role in their journey toward academic success. Academic institutions use the main guidelines to achieve the desired quality of business education for their primary clients. These students entrust their future careers to the University of Cebu by pursuing a degree. It can be inferred that the students expressed satisfaction with the rules and

procedures for enrollment and retention, notwithstanding the existence of course requirements. Therefore, such academic policies are aligned with and parallel to the current learning needs of the new generation of college students and the industry requirements for seeking employment upon completing the BSBA degree. However, some loopholes and shortcomings in the enrolment and retention policies need to be reviewed and enhanced to avoid issues and maintain the quest for attaining UC's brand of providing affordable education to students from all walks of life.

TRANSLATIONAL RESEARCH

The College of Business and Accountancy's efforts to provide quality business education to all its students, particularly those enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program, are ongoing. As the business world continues to evolve and change its standards and norms, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) need to align their Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) and Program Outcomes (POs) because they primarily train and educate students to develop the competencies and skills needed in their future work. To achieve these goals, the academic institution should implement an effective admission policy to enroll students who meet the required standards. Moreover, the school should maintain a program-level retention policy to strike a balance between the business side of running the school and the quality of its graduates. Through this policy, all graduates can meet the required standards. Hence, the significant element in achieving these objectives is ensuring that the admission and retention policies are up-to-date and practical for the current situation. This calls for a proposed framework that will serve as a guide for revisiting and enhancing the admission and retention policies of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program. It will help the Dean, school administrators, faculty, and staff assess if the current program-level policies implemented are still responsive to the needs of the time. The admission and retention programs are the facets of achieving quality business education. Periodic visits and assessments are necessary to ensure the practicality of implementing these policies. The admission will be imposed first, followed by the retention policies. However, they should work in parallel or in tandem to run the BSBA program. Likewise, the challenges arising in implementing these policies should be taken into consideration in updating the most practical admission and retention policies. Obsolete policies will only result in more significant problems that can affect the effectiveness of the BSBA program.

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